

Deliverable
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.2
Workpackage 6

Responsible Partner: 2-AGES, 23-UoS

Description of the task

As part of task 6.2., the deliverable **D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.2** (*Findings presented at one international conference and one national conference*) reports on the contributions by WP6 to scientific conferences. Findings were presented at three conferences of international scope, namely the One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 and 2022 and the ONE Conference 2022. Links to these are provided below:

<https://ohejp2021.com>

<https://ohejp2022.com>

<https://www.one2022.eu>

Description of the deliverable

In 2021 and 2022, a total of three poster presentations were delivered at the ONE Conference in Brussels and at the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting. Further details of these three contributions are displayed below:

- B Gardner, M M Hassan, M Chambers, R M La Ragoine, G Lo Iacono, 2021. “Ecological modelling of microbial communities subject to perturbation”, One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9th-11th June 2021, Copenhagen (Denmark) and online.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915941>
- B Gardner, L C Gonzalez Villeta; J Leng; M M. Hassan; M Chambers; R M La Ragione; G Lo Iacono. 2022. “Mechanistic modelling of microbial communities with insights from an in vitro pig gut model”, One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, 11-13 April, Orvieto (Italy) and online.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6856915>
- B. Gardner; M. M. Hassan; M. Chambers; R. M. La Ragione; G. Lo Iacono 2022. “Modelling the dynamics and long-term stability of perturbed gut microbiota”, ONE Conference 2022, 21-24 June 2022, Brussels (Belgium) and Online.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6860460>.

Confidentiality of the documents

Posters and abstracts are available on Zenodo.